

101112135 - IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP4 – Healthcare Data Standards and Interoperability

D4.1 Data Management Plan (1)

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V0.3	30.08.2023	Revised version, circulated to DMPWG and WP Leaders
V0.4	04.09.2023	Revised version for internal submission of D4.1
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Executive Summary

The IDERHA's Data Management Plan (DMP) provides an overview of the data management policy to be implemented by the project for research data. The DMP encompasses the entire research data life cycle. It describes the types of data to be provided and/or generated, the standards to be used to harmonise/standardise the data, plans for exploitation, sharing and accessibility, as well as the curation, FAIRification (making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), preservation and sustainability of the data.

The development of the first version of the IDERHA DMP (Deliverable (D) 4.1 in Month (M)6) has been an intensive collaborative effort since the project began. Initially, we announced the DMP development as a major project focus at the IDERHA Kick-off Meeting in Berlin, April 18-19, 2023, and we have worked on it systematically, the first version delivered at M6. The current version of the IDERHA DMP was developed under the coordination of the UNILU team, based on extensive discussions conducted among the consortium partners regarding the IDERHA platform's planned functionality and datasets, which may be accessed, used, and updated throughout the length of the IDERHA project. In this process, a representative committee – Data Management Plan Working Group (DMPWG) – was formed to coordinate, review and resolve issues related to the DMP and update it accordingly.

The DMP is a living document and will be updated throughout the project whenever significant changes arise, such as new types of data or changes in the consortium policies or consortium composition. At a minimum, one major update will occur at project-end (D4.4 in M48).

Introduction

In this report we summarise the aim of the IDERHA DMP (D4.1 in M6) and the relevant major steps we performed to develop it, including the challenges and corresponding tackling approaches. We highlight that the DMP development was conducted as an intensive collaborative task across all project work packages (WPs) and highly interconnected with other deliverables (such as the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) analysis - D5.1 in M9 and the WP1 infrastructure description – D1.1 in M12).

Glossary

DMPWG	Data Management Plan Working Group
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DSA	Data Sharing Agreement
EHDS	European Health Data Space
FAIR	Principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
PMO	Project Management Office
WP	Work package

Methods

The development of the first version of the IDERHA DMP (D4.1 in M6) started at the IDERHA Kick-off meeting in Berlin (April 18-19, 2023). Notably, we performed several dedicated activities for the DMP development:

- Creation of the **Data Management Plan Working Group (DMPWG)** - a representative committee formed from project members as a core group responsible for the DMP development. The DMPWG was open to all project members, targeting representatives from work packages: WP1 (infrastructure), WP2 (algorithms and data use), WP3 (cohorts), WP4 (data standards, ontologies, and FAIRification), WP5 (ethical, privacy and legal), WP8 (project management). Specifically, the DMPWG's tasks were to coordinate, review, and resolve issues related to the DMP and update it accordingly. The DMPWG

composition is available in the project SharePoint to all registered project members. At the time of this report (September 2023), DMPWG is composed of 32 project members, from all WPs.

- Organization of WP4 Meetings dedicated to the DMP and identification of project-level responsible members for describing data-related activities: we allocated meetings within WP4 to the DMP, where we initially explained and discussed the needs for the DMP development, including the creation of the DMPWG. For the DMP development, both the DMPWG and WP4 members acted as core members. Then, we reached out to other IDERHA WP members across the whole project; thus, we identified the leaders of data-related work and associated tasks within the IDERHA project, including:
 - o the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) analysis (i.e, Task T5.1): the DPIA-dedicated working group coordinated the input of the DPIA section in DMP,
 - o the Data FAIRification (Tasks T4.1 – T4.6): WP1 and WP4 members worked very closely together and coordinated the input on plans of implementing the FAIR principles within the IDERHA project into DMP,
 - o the Data Access Taskforce that provides ethical and legal compliance support to the needs for data access within and beyond IDERHA. This task force includes representative members from multiple WPs who also participated in the DMP development.
- Organization of several meetings and workshops with other WPs to harmonize the data access related effort, as follows:
 - o **Cross-WPs data-management meetings involving WP4-DMP / WP5-DPIA / WP8-DSA:** we held several meetings involving task leaders from different WPs (specifically WP4, WP5 and WP8) for discussing and addressing needs for several major IDERHA data-related components including DMP, DPIA and Data Sharing Agreement (DSA).
 - o **Organisation of a WP1 Workshop on IDERHA Architecture** (July 20-21, UNILU, Luxembourg) - a group of several WP1 members held a workshop at UNILU, Luxembourg to work on the IDERHA architecture concepts. Key points on data management platform from the workshop are included in DMP.
 - o **Workflow diagram development coordinated by the WP1:** an overview describing the basic workflows within the IDERHA project (together with potential involved users /components and their roles) was developed under the WP1 coordination following the WP1 Workshop and integrated into the DMP.
 - o **Organisation of the data workflow workshop (September 11, 2023, online):** Conducting an online workshop across all WPs to set a common understanding of the data use, access and data flows needed for the execution phase of IDERHA (based on the legal and technical input of the Data Access Taskforce).
- **Using and maintaining the IDERHA data provider table (denoted internally as the “green table”)** which included details on the data resources (name, origin, number of participants, data types, etc.) identified as willing to participate to IDERHA. The green table was provided initially within the project proposal. During the DMP development, the cross-WPs data management groups and Data Access Taskforce worked on confirming information on cohorts and updating this table to collect more information on DMP/DPIA/DSA related aspects; in the DMP we refer to the most up-to-date version of this data source table (reference date 01.09.2023), which will be updated within the project duration.
- **Setting a time plan for the DMP development:** According to our plan, the first DMP draft was available by July 15 to DMPWG members; an extended draft with collected information from the WP1 workshop, WP4 and WP5's input etc. was available by August 9 and was shared with all WPs leaders as well as with the DMPWG members. Given the holiday season, the collection of WPs' feedback continued until August 30, when a complete DMP version was prepared and circulated again among the DMPWG and WP Leaders for final review before the internal submission. On September 4, the DMP was submitted to the IDERHA Project Management Office (PMO) for internal approval. Final revisions and necessary updates have been implemented before the submission by end of September.

Results

The DMP document has been prepared based on [Horizon2020 DMP template](#) and is a living document available internally to all project partners online in IDERHA project portal (Sharepoint) at:

https://lygatureprojectplaza.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/IDERHA/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BFBC28BDD3-CEDC-4323-A9BBF232262585E9%7D&file=IDERHA_DMP.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true.

The current DMP document (v1.0) is delivered as an attachment to this D4.1 report, below.

Discussion

IDERHA is an ambitious large-scale project aiming to provide many innovative solutions for the secondary use of health data. Multiple discussions and alignments between partners are ongoing to specify and prioritize the tasks within IDERHA. The DMP development (D4.1) was considered a key initial effort since the IDERHA Kick-off meeting in Berlin, and the DMP working group kept receiving constant support on this task from the WP4 and the project coordination teams, as well as contributions from project partners, especially from data-related activities.

Development of the DMP at M6 was demanding as it was heavily dependent on detailed inputs from all WPs, whose specific activities and future deliverables are still being actively implemented. For example, the first version of the project architecture (WP1) will be delivered in M12, and until then, intensive discussions on the overall system specification will require finalisation. However, the dual role that UNILU has both the coordinator for the DMP development and the WP1 leader, facilitated the elemental input on the IDERHA infrastructure into DMP.

The consideration of aligning the IDERHA project with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) for the secondary use of data is planned in WP4 (D4.3 in M36). The close collaboration with WP1 and WP4 will facilitate the adoption of EHDS requirements in terms of health data standards and interoperability, data quality frameworks, and FAIRification tools.

Another challenging aspect we faced is that the details on the use cases and data providers' involvement (the input in the "green table") are being still updated and detailed. To address this case, project partners intensified certain discussions to allow answering specific DMP questions; nonetheless the process will continue after the submission of this deliverable and further details will be added in the future versions of the DMP.

Finally, open questions and design aspects are listed in the DMP's action plan section to be reviewed in future DMP releases.

Conclusion

The IDERHA DMP is a living document. The first version of the DMP has been developed in a close collaboration with project partners and agreed among the parties. It will be regularly updated and adapted to the future project's developments and needs. There will be at least one major DMP update as D4.4 at M48. There are no deviations from the project plan.

Repository for primary data

NA

IHI 101112135 – IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP4 – Healthcare data standards and interoperability

D4.1– Data Management Plan

Lead contributor (partner organization)	UNILU
Other contributors	FHI, JJM, LYG, I-HD, VTT, Q1.6, LBG, FHTW, SERGAS, SAS, FISEVI, HULAFE, PMS, ASK, LH, ROCHE, MSB, JVP, JPNV, JJMNV, HYG

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V0.2_comments	25.08.2023	Comments from WPs
V0.3	30.08.2023	Updated version for final review by WPs
V0.3_comments	01.09.2023	Comments
V0.4	01.09.2023	Updated version for internal submission of D4.1
V0.4_comments	26.09.2023	Comments + feedback from PMO
V1.0	27.09.2023	Final (D4.1)

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1 Abstract / Introduction of DMP

This document is a Data Management Plan (DMP) whose purpose is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the consortium regarding the project research data. It will be consistent with the exploitation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) requirements detailed in the IDERHA Consortium Agreement (CA). The DMP will be a living document and will be updated as required throughout the project as the implementation progresses or whenever significant changes arise, such as new types of data or changes in the consortium policies or consortium composition. The current document is the first DMP version, planned as Deliverable (D) 4.1 in Month (M) 6. At a minimum, one update of the DMP will occur in M48 as D4.4. Since several aspects of the IDERHA platform and data flow are still work in progress, the required actions and aspects under discussion have been collected in separate tables (in section 9) along with an indication of the responsible work package, taskforce, or Beneficiary to address them. This table will be reviewed during each subsequent update of the DMP document.

The DMP covers the complete research data life cycle. It describes the types of data that will be provided and/or generated during the project, how they will be curated, standardised, FAIRified, and preserved, as well as how the research data will be made accessible, shared, and exploited. Data processing scenarios in IDERHA together with roles of the partners in the process are introduced. Finally, the DMP also introduces the plans for the sustainability of the data and the platform, together with tools/services/algorithms/codebase developed during the IDERHA project.

This DMP presents an overview of the steps we are taking to ensure quality and interoperability of the IDERHA platform, compliance with the FAIR data principles, and alignment with the emerging European Health Data Space (EHDS) requirements. The DMP also summarises the main guidelines for data security and personal data protection, in line with the Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on the protection of individuals regarding processing personal data, and on free movement of such data (GDPR), other applicable data protection legislation, legislation on data sharing and associated ethics approvals.

In this version of the DMP we focus on the project's execution phase; the guidance for the exploitation phase will be elaborated in the course of the project and included in future versions of the DMP.

1.1 Glossary

A detailed glossary for the terms used in the IDERHA project is being developed by Work Package 5 (WP5) and is available to the project members in the project's SharePoint at [IDERHA GOT UNDER PREPARATION.xlsx](#). The most current version of the glossary [reference date 27/09/2023] is attached as Appendix 1 to this document. In addition, below in Table 1 we provide a brief glossary for the mostly used acronyms to facilitate the understanding of the DMP document.

AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Records
FAIR	Principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCP	Healthcare professional
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
IDERHA	Integration of heterogenous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance
LC	Lung Cancer
PHD	Personal Health Data

Table 1. A list of acronyms used in this DMP document.

2 Project introduction and objectives

In the IDERHA (Integration of heterogenous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance) project we aim to enhance innovation within the EU health care system by developing one of the first pan-European health data spaces. With our solutions, focusing on the field of Lung Cancer (LC), we aim to address the obstacles that currently limit appropriate access to, sharing of, use and reuse of digital health care and patient data. By allowing integration and analysis of health data across sectors and along the continuum of care, we aim to contribute to improved healthcare, i.e., to enable regulatory and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) decision making for integrated health research, and to allow for better meeting of patients' and healthcare professionals' (HCPs) needs.

As defined in the project proposal, the specific objectives of the IDERHA project are to:

- *Enable the transition from a siloed evidence generation and disease treatment approach to a cross-sectorial integrated and more personalised health care strategy in Europe.*
- *Demonstrate that the complementary combination of data standards, infrastructures, tools, and services is possible.*
- *Build the initial critical mass of data providers, data users, and heterogenous health data to demonstrate benefits from connecting and contributing or accessing data.*
- *Assemble and build interoperable services across connected data sources.*
- *Connect multiple public and private data sources and make their heterogeneous data discoverable, accessible, and where possible linkable at patient level for legitimate purposes in primary and secondary use under the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability (FAIR).*
- *Enable federated and central data storage, management, and control, as well as evaluation of personal data with privacy preserving and distributed analytics.*
- *Demonstrate the feasibility and utility of access to and connectivity of heterogenous health data in Lung cancer use cases selected along patient pathway.*
- *Empower patients with access to their own data, receive data requests, consent or withdrawal of access to their own data to other parties.*
- *Provide for sustained long-term access for researchers and developers in the health sector to relevant data under clear, ethical, and legitimate rules.*
- *Pave the path for researchers, including industry, health authorities, payers and HTA agencies to gain access to richer real-world data and enable higher quality evidence, by engaging stakeholders, including patients, HCP's, regulators, HTA bodies in the development of policy recommendations.*
- *Open new, personalised insights and evidence opportunities to benefit from cross-*

continuum of care and access to these Real-World Data (RWD).

- *Develop solutions and policy recommendations that are transferable to other pathologies and health care settings.*

The overall goal of IDERHA project is to facilitate access and reuse of heterogenous health data and it will be demonstrated in use cases selected throughout the lung-cancer patient journey. The IDERHA network infrastructure will connect (WP1) existing data resources at data providers' sites and allow users to access the data, share them and perform their integrative analysis (WP2) through the application of common data standards (WP4) and in conformance with GDPR and regulatory requirements (WP5). Existing (retrospective) datasets will be used by the project partners for the development of analysis algorithms (WP2), as well as to evaluate and demonstrate the value and utility of the IDERHA platform to patients, researchers, regulators, and other stakeholders (WP3). In addition, remote patient monitoring and data access consent management will be enabled with dedicated mobile applications (WP1).

Eventually, in later stages of the project and afterwards, the IDERHA infrastructure and services will demonstrate solutions for prospective data and will showcase how these could be used to help individual patients and their medical healthcare professionals in their diagnostic process, prognosis, and treatment predictions.

Given that IDERHA is a highly data-centric, infrastructural, and collaborative project, data management activities are a central part of our work. The project team is focused on **making both the data and the IDERHA platform's infrastructure FAIR, sustainable and secure**. Data management activities are distributed across several WPs and tasks. Detailed description of the responsibilities can be found in section 5: "Allocation of resources" of this DMP. Specific strategies and plans for different aspects of data management in IDERHA are still under discussions within WPs or tasks. In the current version of the DMP we present the overview of the approaches to be elaborated and detailed within the course of the project by the respective working groups, and we point to the deliverables that will describe the final arrangements. The DMP, as a living document, will reflect the developments as the project progresses.

3 Data Summary

3.1 Data sources

In IDERHA, we plan to have two types of data providers: institutional and individual data providers. A brief introduction on these follows in the current section.

At the project proposal phase, 26 data institutions/services/repositories, who host or who intermediate in collecting and sharing of LC data, have been identified as potential **institutional data providers** within the IDERHA project. A summary characteristic of their data resources can be found in a file denoted internally as the "[green table](#)", available to the project members (not attached to the DMP due to the sensitive nature of some data descriptors). During the course of the IDERHA project, the Data Access Task Force (which was formed from representatives on data management, ethical and legal aspects) initiated further contacts and exchange with these data providers to collect details for characterisation of their data resources in terms of their origin, content, types and formats, access conditions, legal and ethical aspects as well as their applicability in IDERHA's use cases (see section 3.3 below). The updated data characteristics are being collected in a (work-in-progress) "[extended green table](#)", available internally to the project members. More updates on the status and detailed description of provided resources will be included in the next DMP versions.

Out of the 26 institutional data providers, most contain data from the area of clinical care or evaluation of care units; these are clinical cancer registries, composite databases, hospital screening

programmes, etc., with diverse data collection/generation purposes. They accommodate heterogeneous data related to LC covering Electronic Health Records (EHRs) with all/some of: clinical diagnostics and/or therapy data, blood test data, imaging data, general pathology data, molecular genetics, biology data, specific drug treatment data, specific radiotherapy data, patient safety data, patient-reported outcomes (PROMs) and experiences (PREMs) data, as well as occupational data, and environmental data.

Currently the number of LC patients, recruited in 9 European countries since 1998, included in the identified resources reaches ~1.3mln. If all data providers decide to provide access, IDERHA will enable access to retrospective data on these individuals. Additionally, patient recruitment procedures are still ongoing at multiple of the identified institutions, so new data records as well as additional categories of data are planned for collection (see the "green table" for details). Besides, the datasets prospectively collected by the IDERHA partner (Asklepios) for their LC study by means of remote patient monitoring solutions (to be developed by IDERHA's tasks T1.6 and T2.5) will also be accessible. The data management details for these activities will be provided in the future versions of the DMP.

The expected types of research data that will be shared with IDERHA include several categories of low and high dimensional data: clinical and molecular data (such as genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics), image data and patient generated data types, including wearables measurements, PROMs and PREMs, and questionnaires. The data type set will be detailed in the future iterations of the DMP as the scope of collaboration and availability of datasets continue to evolve.

In addition to interconnecting the institutional data providers, IDERHA aims to also offer solutions for **individual data providers** to enable them to share their own resources, so-called **citizen-controlled data**, with other users for specific purposes. With the citizen-controlled data sharing application, citizen users (whether patients or not) can decide what personal health data (PHD) pertaining to themselves is shared with other parties, and for what purposes. PHD may be of two types:

- Acquired and/or stored in data collections at institutional data storages such as hospitals, public or private research organisations, or
- Collected and/or stored directly by private individuals on privately owned devices, e.g., accessed via the citizen-controlled data sharing application.

The individual data providers will be identified during the project by T1.5 and the details about their resources will be provided in the future updates to the DMP.

3.1.1 GDPR roles

Institutional data providers, identified at this timepoint (listed in the "green table"), collect LC data in a primary data collection for different purposes and on legitimate basis which may vary case by case. These providers will be able to decide what happens with the data and with whom it is shared, so they will act as Data Controllers, determining the purposes and the means by which personal data is processed. Whether a data user will be a Joint Controller or Data Processor is currently unknown. This is currently being discussed and will be further clarified by the DPIA, which is a deliverable of IDERHA (D5.1) in M9.

In the case of individual data providers, citizens who hold PHD themselves are the data subjects and, at the same time, the data owners, managing their own PHD sharing. These citizens will be able to choose to make their PHD available to others at their discretion using the citizen-controlled

data sharing application. Hygiaso, the IDERHA partner who will provide this application, described in T1.5, will facilitate access and use of such PHD with desired users at specified conditions for specific purposes. Whether Hygiaso will be a Joint Controller or Data Processor is as yet unknown and will be clarified by the DPIA.

Determination of GDPR roles was added to the table of DMP actions in section 9.1.1.

3.1.2 Data (re)use regulations

IDERHA, as a research project, will enable access to heterogenous health data from existing data resources and, in collaboration with their providers and according to the GDPR and other applicable regulations, IDERHA partners will use some of the data resources for the developments of the platform and its services. We currently only expect secondary data use, i.e., the use of data originally collected for the purpose of clinical care, which can be retrospective (already existing), prospective (still to be collected) or a combination of both. Within the current timeline/scope of IDERHA the use of prospective data (or potential 'primary use' of data, should it be acquired in the future) is planned for feasibility/evaluation/proof-of-concept/demonstration purposes only, and will not be used for clinical decision making. Hence all data used for this validation/evaluation is used in the sense of 'secondary use'.

The citizen-controlled data sharing application will provide technical means for PHD sharing and hence qualifies as data intermediation service per the EU Data Governance Act (DGA) and will have to be certified. Some but not all requirements to such data intermediaries are known today, yet other requirements will evolve per EC delegated acts such as data quality or security standards, as well as mandatory data formats and scope. As reasonable best assumptions regarding such requirements, the sharing application will be developed and managed in anticipation of regulatory requirements corresponding to the requirements of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) for Class IIa devices (medical information systems – not used for direct vital/high risk decision making). At the initial stage of development, mock, synthetic data or de-identified PHD will be used. The data will be shared for Research Use Only (RUO), which is compatible for the IDERHA use cases in the execution phase.

3.1.3 Legal bases and data access

The data access and other data use conditions will depend on the data providers. Specific scenarios, satisfying project requirements and with sufficient lawful basis for processing, are still being discussed in Data Access Task Force group and will be defined in the next months. The priority is given to the Spanish, Finnish and German data providers who, as Beneficiaries of the project, are going to provide (federated) access to datasets for the initial AI/ML use cases (see section 3.3 below), i.e., HULAFE, SERGAS, SAS, VTT, and MSB.

According to our current knowledge (as of the 1st IDERHA workshop on data flows on 11.09.2023), in accordance with the Spanish Law, the pseudonymised personal data from Spanish hospitals can be used in IDERHA for the purpose of biomedical research (provided that certain steps of pseudonymisation procedure are fulfilled, e.g., technical and functional separation of the actors involved, commitment to confidentiality and non-re-identification, preventive security measures, which is the case for HULAFE, SERGAS, and SAS). For the Finnish data, the national regulations allow the use of pseudonymised data in research but they require that all results be manually reviewed before releasing. Hence, the data provided by VTT cannot be used in the training of federated AI/ML models (which requires multiple iterations of data exchange between the federated and centralised node), and thus can only be used for the validation of the models trained with Spanish and German data. The exact data access conditions for the case of German data from MSB

is subject to ongoing discussions.

Detailed descriptions of the specific data access scenarios, data use conditions and data flows will be elaborated and described in Data Protection and Impact Assessment (DPIA) document (delivered as D5.1 at M9). Upon establishing the key data processing steps, the legal basis for each relevant step, and GDPR roles and responsibilities of Beneficiaries and 3rd parties, they will be also covered in the next versions of the DMP.

In all citizen use cases, the legal basis for PHD data sharing is going to be explicit consent (Art 9, GDPR).

3.2 Data models and formats

Data standardisation, harmonisation and formatting will be defined and guided by the work of WP4. After performing an in-depth survey amongst the data providers on the existing data types and formats in use as well as collecting requirements from WP1-3,5,6 and their use cases, a set of recommendations will be provided in T4.2 (as D4.2 in M24) to govern the handling of different data types in IDERHA. The goal is to provide guidance on standards, data models and migration paths to ensure quality and interoperability of the IDERHA platform, compliance with the FAIR data principles, and alignment with emerging EHDS requirements in T4.1 (as D4.3 in M36).

An overview of the data types and data description standards used by the potential institutional data providers, collected in the initial project survey, is presented in Table 2. At the time of this DMP preparation, the interoperability standards most likely to be used by IDERHA are the following: FHIR as the non-imaging health informatics exchange standard, DICOM for imaging communication and OMOP as the storage model for non-imaging data.

Data Type	# Providers	Data description standards (as declared)
Electronic Health Records (EHR)	13	OMOP, HL7/FHIR
Clinical cancer care data on diagnostics and/or therapy	24	OMOP, HL7/FHIR, "structured", "unstructured"
General pathology data	16	
Specific drug treatment data	9	
Laboratory results data	11	OMOP, "structured"
Imaging data	18	DICOM
Specific radiotherapy data		DICOM, OMOP
Molecular genetics & biology data	15	OMOP, "structured", "unstructured"
PROMs	2	"structured"
PREMs	1	
Environmental exposure & socioeconomic data	3	OMOP

Table 2. An overview of the data types collected by institutional data providers, count of their providers and data description standards currently used.

For citizen-controlled PHD various data formats are currently used depending on the diagnostic or medical modality. PHD is typically collected from multiple sources. Initially, PHD exchange functionality will focus on CT image data in DICOM format. Gradually further data modalities and respective formats will be added (i.e., including OMOP) as required.

As we intend to interconnect heterogenous, multi-source data resources, we might deal with data type cases for which no established compatible standards can be utilised or adopted, such as specific citizen-generated health data originating from consumer and/or medical devices such as wearables and telemonitoring applications used in home environment. Such data may come in varying formats and may require to be connected to the citizen's application and made accessible.

We will investigate existing recommendations and ongoing initiatives (e.g., ICHOM community for PROMs data) to identify the best approaches to handle them. If these prove insufficient, some extensions to the standards might be proposed and developed by IDERHA in collaboration with the respective communities (e.g., OMOP-CDM).

3.3 Use cases

IDERHA WP2 will use the data provided by the Data Provider partners for the development of AI/ML algorithms and workflows as well as patient focus applications. Four use cases (UC) have been defined to demonstrate the value of the integration of heterogeneous health data of the platform and its use for patients, health professionals and research community:

- UC1: Personalised LC risk profiling based on:
 - AI/ML algorithm using multimodal data sets (including EHR)
 - AI/ML algorithm using DICOM data from CT images
- UC2: Personalised LC diagnosis on AI/ML analysis of CT images
- UC3: Personalised LC prognosis (progression free survival, overall survival)
- UC4: Remote monitoring of the well-being and patient engagement of LC patients using device technology/ application in an at-home environment.

For the development, training and evaluation of the algorithms, data from Spanish, Finnish and German data providers (i.e., HULAFE, SERGAS, SAS, VTT, MSB) will be used. The data for two initial use cases UC1 and UC3 will be mapped to the OMOP common data model, according to guidelines defined by WP4. UC2 will employ images in DICOM format. For the initial stages of the development, and before the data access and data use conditions are clarified between the parties, the possibility of using synthetic data provided by the partners and preserving statistical characteristics from original, real-world data is being explored.

Validation of AI/ML algorithms will be performed using so called pseudo-prospectively collected data, whereby a time stamp will be selected beyond which all new data collected at the data partners will be aggregated for the only purpose of algorithm validation. For UC4, a clinical study protocol will be put in place, allowing for the capture of prospectively collected data sets needed for value demonstration.

The expected output of the WP2 use cases will be AI/ML model predictions that will be generated “on the fly” by the users and returned to them via the platform. The characterisation and handling of the results generated as part of the model validation procedures in WP2 for reference use cases will be investigated, and the details will be provided in the next DMP version.

In addition to the above-described UCs of AI/ML coordinated by WP2, IDERHA will work a PHD use case led by WP1 T1.5:

- UC: citizen-controlled PHD sharing, which will involve:
 - Citizen’s consent to a request for re-use of their PHD contained in a data collection of a data provider. The intended user could be the current data provider or a 3rd party.
 - Data Linking (exchanging reference to the same subject’s PHD across two or more datasets) based on a reference key or consent being shared among involved parties by means of access tokens to source PHD.
 - Citizen’s request for a copy of their PHD held with a data provider, to receive their PHD into their own environment where the citizen is going to be an autonomous

manager of their own PHD.

For this use case, similarly to WP2, at the initial stage of development the use of mock, synthetic data or de-identified PHD will be explored.

3.4 IDERHA Platform design

A primary objective of IDERHA is to develop one of the first pan-European health data spaces. This will allow transition of the existing isolated data platforms into a federated inter-connected ecosystem. Thus, in line with the project's objectives and the growing need for a decentralised data approach, diverse data resources will be connected via IDERHA without centralizing all data in a single database. The data will continue to stay in their source locations, under control of their host institutions. The data resources will be linked, made discoverable and available through the IDERHA federated infrastructure to expose them to the platform's users (patients, healthcare professionals, researchers in the LC field), e.g., via federated data catalogue and analysis pipelines.

From a technical point of view, the term "data space" is an umbrella for many different processes that must work together to enable secure exchange and use of health data. To support these processes, we will develop and/or reuse a set of technical components working together as the IDERHA platform, including (but not limited to):

- connectors to institutional data repositories with heterogenous health data,
- connectors to individual's data storages with citizen-controlled data,
- remote computational nodes with access to data resources,
- central computational node(s) with computing capacity for orchestrating centralised federated learning and analysis processes,
- platform user management service,
- citizen identification service,
- citizen consenting service,
- data catalogue(s) and algorithm catalogue(s),
- platform's main portal (e.g., an entry point to the catalogues)
- citizen application for consent management and access to own PHD.

Several workflows are being considered when designing the IDERHA platform's functionality and architecture. An overview of the IDERHA platform's main components and their functions is shown in Figure 1 (below) for two basic scenarios of i) federated data analysis use case and ii) citizen data access use case.

- The core scenario focuses on solving the UCs defined in WP2 by enabling the use of health records from institutional data providers for data analysis by means of centralised federated learning. In this scenario anonymised/pseudonymised record level data are processed in the secure research environments of their host institutions, and only derived data (model parameters and predictions) are exposed to the users (researchers). The AI/ML processing optimises model parameters in a privacy preserving way, by exchanging derived data between the federated computing nodes (at the data providers' sites) and central computing node of IDERHA (hosted by UNILU, the IDERHA partner).
- Additional scenarios considered in IDERHA relate to the citizen-controlled PHD sharing use case and include allowing citizens to access their personal health records from institutional repositories via the citizen app, as well as to manage consent for sharing their data with other IDERHA users for specific purposes via a citizen consenting service. Here, citizens will be free to choose where to store their data and with whom to share it. The citizen-controlled data sharing application will manage the access to PHD in data provider's storage, be it organisations in the health sector or a citizen storage.

Citizen controlled storage may vary substantially (cloud or on device, operating system, jurisdiction, rigor of security). We will aim to offer citizens a storage space in an EU-based cloud or a jurisdiction with data protection adequacy which is adequate from a security perspective. Ultimately it will be citizens' choice as to whether they store their PHD in their own environment or the one which will be offered to them through the citizen-controlled data sharing application. To ensure appropriate protection, regardless of storage environment, PHD transferred via the application will be stored in an encrypted format in the destination storage.

In the citizen use case data is shared directly between the data provider and the data user. Access keys and transaction data are intermediated via the citizen-controlled data sharing application.

The system architecture combining the desired processes and functionalities into the IDERHA platform is being developed by WP1 in collaboration with and based on other WPs' recommendations (such as the guidelines to satisfy the legal obligations, ensure compliance with the FAIR data principles, and align with the emerging EHDS requirements). The architecture will be delivered by T1.1 as a deliverable (D1.1) at M12 of the project, and further elaborated at M24 (as D1.3). Practical demonstration of selected data flows in IDERHA platform will be done as D1.2 at M18.

IDERHA DMP

Potential types

- Researcher
- Healthcare professional
- Citizen

- IDERHA portal
- IDERHA citizen's mobile application

- Hospital
- Research centre
- Citizen-controlled storage (e.g., consumer devices)

Potential roles

- (Researcher) performs analyses to answer research questions (by choosing algorithms and data)
- (Healthcare professional) requests access to individual patient's health data to inform diagnosing and treatment
- (Healthcare professional) performs analysis of individual patient's health data to get predictions based on federated data analyses
- (Citizen) requests access to their own data from institutional data providers
- (Citizen) approves access to their own data for other users and specific purposes

- Displays catalogues of data and algorithms
- Provides user authentication services
- Enables requesting data and analyses
- Displays analysis results
- (Citizen app) allows for consent to personal data sharing

- Hosts central data catalogue and algorithm catalogue
- Centralises info about federated nodes
- Aggregates metadata about federated data
- Intermediates between clients and federated nodes
- Enables data linking and cross-referencing
- Distributes tasks to federated nodes
- Acts as central computational node for federated analyses

- Is hosted at data provider's site
- Hosts a local data catalogue
- Interacts with data providers
- Acts as a computational node for federated analyses

- Hosts a health data storage
- Authorises data access
- Enforces data access policies and compliance with consent

Figure 1. An overview of the IDERHA platform with its potential actors/components and their roles. Two exemplary scenarios / data flows are presented: **A.** federated data analysis use case, **B.** citizen data use case (PHD access)

4 FAIR data

In IDERHA, we will deal with heterogeneous health data with the main goal of making the data interconnected and accessible to the platform users, and of using the data internally for the development of the platform and demonstrating its value (in particular, by analysis tools for use cases by WP2/WP3). We will apply and develop approaches (recommendations, workflows, services) that support data handling in a FAIR, sustainable and secure way.

Below, we briefly present initial steps towards data FAIRification. Details will be included in updated DMP versions.

4.1 Findability

Research data findability will be ensured through the following properties:

- Rich metadata describing the data resources (datasets, workflows, tools and containerisation recipes) according to technical and domain specific standards (to be defined by WP1 and WP4, respectively, during the project) will be used to document their identification, characteristics, provenance, versioning, use conditions, etc.
- IDERHA's central catalogue (based on interoperability standards such as DCAT2) and platform's search service will enable users to interrogate metadata information and discover the federated data resources.
- The citizen-controlled data sharing application may operate a data catalogue containing meta data on the citizen's PHD or provide a service to query availability of the citizens' data in a privacy preserving way. The application will also connect to and interoperate with the IDERHA data catalogue to support data discovery. [No PHD data will be held on the sharing application itself. Ephemeral data storage/processing of aggregate PHD may exceptionally be required for data requests which cannot fully be evaluated/processed de-centrally.]
- IDERHA's Data Linking and Cross-referencing services will support legal and ethical connecting of personal data to enhance findability of personal data.
- Public source code repositories will be used for all open-source developments in IDERHA, especially for results related to the code base for central platform architecture in WP1 and AI/ML workflows WP2.
- IDERHA resources and results will be advertised in the project's portal, social media, during events of related communities, etc. to make them discoverable to the users.

4.2 Accessibility

The IDERHA platform aims to connect and make accessible federated resources of retrospective and newly generated data. Federated data analysis services will be provided to facilitate data analysis across the IDERHA-enabled network of interoperable data sites.

- Metadata for data resources and data analysis methods will be openly available via the IDERHA data catalogue, including instructions how to get access to the data.
- We will be working with the aim of as open as possible, given the legal, ethical and policy restrictions. The Data Access Taskforce within IDERHA is investigating the data access scenarios and will provide recommendations on the required data sharing and data access agreements between the data providers, IDERHA Partners and 3rd parties.
- IDERHA will provide a service for user authentication and authorisation to facilitate data

access. The service will integrate with identity providers by using known industry standards (such as OpenID Connect and SAML).

- Citizen-controlled PHD will be accessible with access keys that the user receives upon consent of that citizen to the requested processing as facilitated by the citizen-controlled data sharing application.
- IDERHA will offer a number of predefined analysis types and pretrained AI/ML models for specific use cases (UC1-UC4), previously approved by the project partners and data providers; in this way, we aim to simplify data accessing procedures at the data providers, and to improve the researcher access to project data.

4.3 Interoperability

To ensure interoperability of the data, we plan to

- Align with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) interoperability requirements (to be recommended by WP4 in T4.1 and delivered as D4.3 in M36) by identifying and following ongoing initiatives and evolving regulations.
- Use common established standards for data representation (to be recommended by WP4 in T4.2), in particular in domain-specific data modelling (e.g. OMOP/FHIR/CDISC for medical data, DICOM for imaging data) and data description (controlled terminologies, ontologies), technical standards (e.g., file formats, encoding, encryptions). This will be detailed in D4.2 at M24.
- Collaborate with relevant communities (including OHDSI community for OMOP data model) to extend existing standards whenever needed to handle all required data types; we will also openly disseminate the results of the work together with sufficient documentation for its adoption and reuse. This will be detailed in IDERHA data standards manual, delivered as D4.2 at M24 or, at the latest, in the final version of DMP (D4.4) at M48.
- Build the IDERHA platform infrastructure from existing open-source implementations of known standards (e.g., Elixir Cloud SDK, Eclipse Data Space Connectors) and contribute to their further development. This will be detailed in platform's architecture deliverables D1.1 (M12) and D1.3 (M24), and the lessons learnt will be summarised in IDERHA's future recommendations report D1.5 at M58.
- Build the IDERHA AI/ML Learning Infrastructure based on algorithms developed in WP2 by leveraging existing open-source libraries (e.g., Flower) and training the algorithms in a federated manner.
- The citizen-controlled data sharing application will connect to IDERHA platform's connectors to exchange data transferred and IDERHA services such as the data catalogue. The data sharing platform will also offer endpoints for IDERHA Partners and 3rd parties to interoperate with citizens and access their PHD.

4.4 Reusability

Increasing reusability of the health data is the central goal of the IDERHA platform. To achieve it, specifically we plan to

- Thoroughly define and transparently describe all ethical and legal aspects for primary (if any) and secondary use of data accessed through IDERHA on behalf of its users (IDERHA Partners and 3rd parties).
- Perform data quality assessments on health data using the IDERHA data quality framework (to be defined in T4.5 as D4.5). This framework will contain most used data

quality dimensions based on academic literature and best practices, e.g., the data quality frameworks of the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS) project. The aim of this framework and assessment to assure that the data being (re)used is of a high quality.

- Conduct a data quality requirement analysis tailored to the specific use cases data quality needs. This will ensure that the data being (re)used meets the objectives and fit for purpose question for each UC. The details will be given by T4.5 in WP4 that will collaborate with T5.2 which is focused on the ethical aspects of AI regulations.
- Validate and evaluate the prediction performance of AI algorithms for use cases in WP2 by standard data resampling approaches (cross-validation) as well as a time-split validation (for a pseudo-prospective validation).
- For the citizen-controlled data app, to ensure reusability, the source and unmutated nature of data shared will be cryptographically ensured by Data Quality features. In the advanced stage of development (in T1.5), the data sharing application will include the development and implementation of Data Quality features.

5 Allocation of resources

Data management activities are a central part of the IDERHA project and are distributed across several WPs and tasks. Thus, a lot of resources is dedicated to make the data FAIR, sustainable and secure.

Multiple partners in IDERHA have rich experience with FAIR data management. To additionally support implementation of FAIR across all WPs, a dedicated task (WP4, T4.8) is being carried out in IDERHA to provide training on standards and methods. The task will also provide coaching in case of advanced implementation problems.

Data curation will be carried out by respective data providers and standardised data will be made available for IDERHA use cases. We will also rely on the data providers' infrastructure to provide the necessary resources (e.g., computational power for analysis algorithms within) needed to setup and the local nodes of IDERHA.

5.1 List of Responsibilities

- WP1 will build the IDERHA Platform Infrastructure to enable findability, accessibility, and reuse of interoperable research data. They will also contribute to FAIRness of the non-research data produced in WP1, in particular the code base for the IDERHA platform.
- WP2 will build data analysis pipelines for the IDERHA Use Cases to facilitate reuse of research data. They will also contribute to FAIRness of the non-research data produced in WP2, in particular the code base for IDERHA analysis pipelines.
- WP3 orchestrates building of the federation of data providers and participates in identification of data types and standards required for findability, interoperability, and reusability of research data.
- WP4 is responsible for coordinating the applicability of FAIR principles of research data in the IDERHA platform. This WP will design and execute most of the FAIR data management strategy in line with current good scientific practices to meet the needs of the digital health care:
 - T4.1 (M1-M60): creating EHDS interoperability framework,
 - T4.2 (M1-M60): recommendation on data exchange standards and models,
 - T4.3 (M1-M48): evaluating and improving the FAIRness of metadata and data,

- T4.4 (M12-M60): recommendations on tools to generate IDERHA-ready data (optimised for findability, interoperability, and utility for machine learning),
- T4.5 (M1-M60): data quality assessment,
- T4.6 (M42-M60): sustainability of the data and platform,
- T4.7 (M1-M48): developing and maintaining the DMP,
- T4.8 (M1-M50): providing knowledge and skills to IDERHA Partners to support implementation of FAIR.
- WP5 will enable research data reuse by ensuring that it is managed according to ethical and legal requirements:
 - T5.1 (M1-M60): compliance with GDPR and national laws, monitoring roles and responsibilities in data handling process, performing the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) analysis,
 - T5.2 (M1-M60): ethical and transparent AI,
 - T5.3 (M1-M60): data reuse strategies and obstacles.
- WP6 will support research data reuse within and outside of the IDERHA project by monitoring implementation of the policies, identifying gaps and obstacles, and building consensus around improved recommendations for data reuse, which will be proposed to the broader external community for advancing of heterogenous health data research.
- WP7 will support research data reuse through communication, dissemination, and stakeholder management. They will also contribute to monitoring and improving FAIRness, sustainability, and reliability of the project results through dissemination activities and supporting their exploitation.
- WP8 will review overall data and software resources FAIRness (as quantified using the FAIRplus data set maturity analyses in T4.3).
- IDERHA data providers will be involved in FAIRification process by participating in the activities to identify data standards and access procedures, as well as by implementing data standards for their resources. They will be engaged in setting up the IDERHA Infrastructure by connecting their data resources to the network, and continuing to host, secure and manage data access.

5.2 Long-term data sustainability plan

Sustainability of the platform after the end of the project is one of the main priorities for IDERHA, and therefore it will be tackled from the start:

- WP8 will be responsible for the managing the overall sustainability strategy for all IDERHA data and software resources with solutions developed with the frame of T8.5 and in associated sustainability working groups and task forces which may be established during the project. The template for sustainability will be based on the experiences of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) community and the “Be SuRe” recommendations framework (<https://zenodo.org/record/8247376>).
- WP3, via the IDERHA strategy of learning by doing, addresses the concrete needs of demonstrators which will help stakeholder organisations better understand the inherent scalability and translatability potential of our approach.
- WP7 will build stakeholder engagement needed in the development, as well in the operational phase and in the long-term to secure the sustainability. They will contribute to develop and support the implementation of a strategic plan for the optimal exploitation and sustainability to ensure the long-term impact of the IDERHA project results, incl. early

use beyond pilot initiatives.

- Long-term sustainability of data and platform strategy for IDERHA will be elaborated in WP4, T4.5 (M42-M60). The task will develop sustainability strategy for the databases, analysis portal and related outputs (results, tools, software modules and algorithms) after project completion. UNILU, in cooperation with ELIXIR Luxembourg Node, will enable archiving and preserving the available data and results generated within IDERHA.
- All Open Source Software Results generated within the project will be made available through public repositories.
- Final sustainability strategy will be developed by WP8 in T8.5 and delivered as D8.2.
- Recommendations for future sustainable infrastructure development based on the lessons learnt from IDERHA data and analysis platform will be delivered in D1.5.
- Data providers are responsible for local sustainability (hosting, securing, and archiving the data for long term preservation after the project), assisted by WP8.

6 Data protection and security

6.1 Data security standards

The data platform will naturally emphasize security and data privacy, in close collaboration with all WPs and data providers. A cross-WP task force will be established, mainly including members of WP1 and WP5, to specifically focus on technical data security and privacy measures. The necessary solutions will be designed and included in the platform's architecture. The cross-WP task force will be responsible for reviewing and monitoring of the procedures on a regular basis (at least bi-annually) and reporting periodically on the measures taken. The IDERHA platform will incrementally develop the regulatory control framework, ensuring adequate data protection (commensurate to the data and use cases handled) and regulations (as these become effective and applicable).

The means considered in IDERHA to ensure data security include (but are not limited to):

- Data anonymisation/pseudonymisation mechanisms will be used/implemented by data provider sites.
- Approved privacy preserving algorithms and data workflows will be developed. Solutions for federated data analysis use cases (WP2) will only work with pseudonymized data and will strictly ensure privacy of patient-level data.
- Federated computing nodes will be hosted at data providers sites so that all processing happens locally, and only derived aggregated data are shared outside the site. For federated data analysis use cases (WP2), no PHD is allowed to leave the data providers' site.
- IDERHA platform will be connected to data providers infrastructure via components providing data access control mechanisms, to make sure that a data storage is accessed in a controlled and authorised way.
- All IDERHA platform components will communicate via secure and end-to-end encrypted connections.
- IDERHA will implement secure authentication and authorization mechanisms for management of platform users (researchers, patients).
- Based on the user token it will be possible to verify the identity of the user at each stage of the process.
- Each service will produce an audit trail/log to record all data related actions performed by user or service.
- Patients will be identified to eIDAS level substantial or high to securely authenticate and

authorize patients for access to personal data.

- For the citizen-controlled data sharing solution, we expect that regulatory requirements (such as appropriate underlying processes regarding quality and risk management of the respective devices required for Medical Device Regulations (MDR)) will crystalize for Data Intermediaries, such as the data intermediation service for the citizen app. We anticipate that ISO13485 (Quality Management System for Medical Devices) and ISO14971 (Risk Management for Medical Devices) or equivalent will become mandatory and therefore proactively and gradually develop to corresponding levels by implementing such minimal procedures early on.
- Given the sensitivity of actual PHD sharing, cyber security requirements consistent with ISO 27001/2 will be implemented to ensure good practice standards in developing and managing the citizen-controlled data sharing solution. At Hygiaso, all development happens on protected and dedicated devices and development environment under an explicit IT Policy with appropriate professional cyber security monitoring and ongoing upgrades to the IT environment as they emerge (e.g., upgrades and security patches).
- For the citizen-controlled data sharing solution, we aim to establish a control framework early on which covers all necessary elements (cyber security, quality, risk management) with minimal overhead. When we enter the phase of actual PHD being shared via the platform, additional controls will be included into the established control framework as necessary to always ensure appropriate protection of PHD.
- The Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) will serve as an ongoing tool to periodically reassess the level of protection and adapt to the required level of PHD protection.

6.2 Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

IDERHA WP5 translates the analysis of data flows across the sites and partners, as defined in this Data Management Plan, into a consistent set of roles and responsibilities regarding personal data handling (Processor/Controller roles). This will allow the development of a generic Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) framework following Art.35 of GDPR and support the conduct of DPIAs by each relevant partner, collate risk mitigations and oversee their adoption. These DPIAs and associated risk analyses will enable us:

- to develop and educate partners on a code of practice for accessing, using and communicating personal data, including compliance with the terms negotiated with each data source contributing to IDERHA.
- to develop a GDPR compliant data protection policy, especially regarding minimisation of genetic and imaging data, anonymisation and pseudonymisation standards, access controls and communication, providing support to the demonstration sites.
- to work with WP1 and WP2 to (i) ensure the effective implementation of data security measures including review of continuous security monitoring procedures and reporting to responsible Data Protection Officers (DPOs) and (ii) implement continuous security monitoring and reporting procedures.

The DPIA is being developed by T5.1 and will be delivered as D5.1 at M9. Further details relevant to the DMP will be included in the next DMP versions.

7 Ethical aspects

WP5 is dedicated and responsible for coordinating the work related to ethical issues bearing on the IDERHA, in collaboration with other WPs. The scope of this work is multifaceted, encompassing governance, and data protection aspects, alongside strictly ethical considerations. An overarching objective of the work in WP5 is to ensure respect for the rights, freedoms, and reasonable expectations of the data subjects whose personal data are used in the IDERHA.

Specific attention will be given (but not limited) to the following aspects:

- Ethical and transparent AI development and use: For the models developed in WP2, the explainable AI methods will be used to understand the influence of individual features on a model's prediction. This will be preceded by the input data quality assessment (T4.5) to ensure their 'fit-for-purpose'. In addition, T5.2 will provide ethical, transparency and quality oversight for the whole development to ensure compliance with the emerging European ethical principles for AI.
- AI risk assessment and trustworthiness: For all AI/ML tools, the user experience will be evaluated to indicate the value of each tool to the clinician experience (T3.5). Extra oversight will be taken to minimise the chance of AI/ML related risks, such as:
 - Privacy risks beyond GDPR, e.g., statistical disclosure control on aggregated data,
 - Misuse of AI, including application outside an algorithm's 'competence' or outside any licence terms,
 - Failure to ensure AI/ML algorithms are applied appropriately and with suitable oversight,
 - The potential to restrict access to care for certain sub-populations,
 - Causing unnecessary public concerns through poor communications of IDERHA and/or AI/ML opportunities and risks.
- Cross-domain linking of personal data: Personal data records will be linked across multiple datasets based on the consent of the subject concerned only (T1.2); necessary safeguards will be defined and put in place to exclude/minimise the risk of potential subject re-identification.

IDERHA also aims to follow and to work towards ensuring compliance with the planned EU regulations in the field.

8 Other issues

8.1 Non-research data management

In addition to managing the IDERHA research data (as described in previous sections), we will rely on GDPR-compliant processes while also adhering to the Consortium Agreement (e.g., protection of results, other fundamental IPR matters, dissemination and publication policies etc.) to manage data and information generated within the project. This includes information or data generated by various WPs (e.g. surveys or process documentation, recording meetings for notetaking, taking public comments on draft reports, etc.) and information disseminated internally and externally (including communication internal to the project consortium and external with the scientific community, convening meetings with individuals outside the consortia, such as healthcare professionals, industry, workshop reports, meeting minutes, interviews, surveys etc.). This non-research data and information generated as part of the IDERHA project will be stored on the Project's SharePoint site, which are only accessible to registered project participants.

9 Updates of this Document and feedback

This DMP is a living document and will be reviewed and updated throughout the project whenever significant changes arise. At a minimum, one major update will occur at M48 as D.4.4.

9.1 Action plan

During the DMP development, we identified several action items as well as potential approaches and responsible within the project to address them. We provide this information specifically below.

9.1.1 Overview of required actions

Required action	Responsible for implementation
Determine data access scenarios and required corresponding agreements	Data Access Taskforce
Determine data flows	WP1-WP5
Determine GDPR roles	WP1-WP5
Establish a cross-WP Data Security Taskforce	WP1, WP5

Table 3: Collective actions following from this DMP.

9.1.2 Open design aspects to be reviewed in the DMP

Open aspect	Responsible for further detailing
High level guidance on exploitation phase	WP7
Characterise individual data providers	T1.5
Minimal data quality, risk and security requirements for health data held and shared	Data Controllers and Processors
Data models and formats	WP4

Table 4: Overview of design aspects requiring further detailing in the next versions of the DMP.

10 Conclusion

The released version of the data management plan has been set up and agreed among the parties.

11 Deviation

There are no deviations from the project plan.

Glossary of Terms	
Abbreviation	Definition
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (data)
HTA	Health Technology Assessments
HCP	Health Care Professionals
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EHDS	European Health Data Space
RWD	Real-world data
RWE	Real-world evidence
HMA	Heads of Medicines Agencies
EMA	European Medicines Agency
BDSG	Big Data Steering Group
IDERHA	Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance
EU MDR	EU Medical Device Regulation
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
IMI EHDEN	European Health Data and Evidence Network
IMI FAIR Plus	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable Plus Consortium
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PREMS/ PROMS	Patient reported experience measures/Patient Reported Outcome Measures
R&I	Research and Innovation Maturity
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
CARE	patient care, patient monitoring, patient consent
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
EHR	Electronic Health Record
HTD	Harmonized Trust Database
OMOP-CDM	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model
CARE	Dedicated platforms for patient care, patient monitoring, patient consent
DATF	Data Access Task force
PIT	Project and Interdependencies Tracker
CDN	Clinical Data Network
IDAGC	Integrated Data Access Governance Council
PAC	Project Asset Continuity team
AD	Alzheimer's disease
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ACI	AC Immune
ADA-M	Automatable Discovery and Access Matrix
ADAS-Cog	The Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale–Cognitive

IDERHA DMP Appendix 1

ADDI	AD Data Initiative
ADL	Activities of Daily Living
ADSC	Alzheimer's Disease Cooperative Study
ADWB	Alzheimer's Disease Workbench
ADWBEPND	Alzheimer's Disease work bench European Platform for Neurodegenerative Diseases
AE	Alzheimer Europe
AETIONOMY	(IMI) Organising Knowledge about Neurodegenerative Disease Mechanisms for the Improvement of Drug Development and Therapy
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
ALS	amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
AMYPAD	AMYloid imaging to Prevent Alzheimer's Disease research initiative
AP	Activator Protein
API	Application Programming Interface
APOE	Apolipoprotein E (gene)
ATN	Amyloid, Tau and Neurodegeneration
BASE1	β -site amyloid precursor protein cleaving enzyme 1 (gene)
BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
BIOMARKAPD	Biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease
BioShare	Biobank Standardisation and Harmonisation for Research Excellence in the European Union
BMD	BMD Software LDA
BPB	Best Practices for Biobanking
C path consortium	Critical Path consortium
C1q	Complement component 1q
C1qR	Complement C1q Receptor
C2	Complement component 2
C4d	Complement Component C4d
C5	Complement component 5
C5a	Complement component 5a
CAA	Cerebral Amyloid Angiopathy
CBD	Cortical-Basal Degeneration
CBG-MEB	Dutch Medicines Evaluation Board
CCS	Cohort Classification Scheme
CDE	Common Data Elements
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CDR-SB	Clinical Dementia Rating scale Sum of Boxes
CDS	Clinical Data Science
CFHR5	Complement Factor H Related 5 (gene)
CHMP	Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use
CHUV	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois
CLSI	Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute
CNS	Central Nervous System
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service

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CP	CeruloPlasmin
CPATH	Critical Path Institute
CPP	Critical Path for Parkinson's consortium
CR2	Complement receptor 2 (gene)
CRC	Colorectal Cancer Cohort
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CRP	Clinical Research Platform
CS	Case Study
CSF	CerebroSpinal Fluid
CTI	Centre for Translational Informatics
CTMM	Center for Translational Molecular Medicine
DSAC	Data and Sample Access Committee
DAISY	Digital Accessible Information System
DataShield	Data Aggregation Through Anonymous Summary-statistics from Harmonised Individual-level Databases
DCAT	Design, Components, Assembly, and Testing
DDF	Dementia Discovery Fund
DKFZ	German Cancer Research Center
DLB	Dementia with Lewy Bodies
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNC	Department of Clinical Neurosciences
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DPUK	Dementias Platform UK
DSAC	Data and Sample Access Committee
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
DUO	Data Use Ontology
DZNE	German Center for Neurodegenerative diseases
EADC	European AD Consortium
EATRIS	European Advanced Translational Research Infrastructure in medicine
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EEA	European Economic Area
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EJP-RD	European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases
ELEG	Ethical & Legal Expert Group
ELISA	Enzyme-Linked ImmunSorbent Assay
ELIXIR	European Life-Science Infrastructure
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Implications
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EMIF	European Medical Information Framework

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EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPAD	European prevention of Alzheimer's dementia consortium
EPND	European Platform for Neurodegenerative Diseases
EREG	External Regulator Expert Group
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERLG	EPND Regulatory Leadership Group
ESAB	External Stakeholder Advisory Board
ETL	Extract-Transform-Load
eTRIKS	European Translational Information and Knowledge management Services
EU	European Union
EUCAN	Europe and Canada (EUCAN) Business Unit
EUCOPE	European Confederation of Pharmaceutical Entrepreneurs
EU-PEARL	EU Patient- cEntric clinicAl tRial pLatform
EWGPWD	European Working Group of People with Dementia
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (data)
FDA	(US) Food and Drug Administration
FDSA	Federated Data Sharing Appliance
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
FTD	FrontoTemporal Dementia
FTD	FrontoTemporal Degeneration
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GAAIN	Global Alzheimer's Association Interactive Network
GAIA-X	project on the development of a federation of data infrastructure and service providers for Europe with the objective of ensuring a European digital sovereignty.
GA	General Assembly
GCC	Genomics Coordination Center
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEN2PHEN	Genotype to Phenotype Databases: a Holistic Approach (EU project)
GV	Gates Ventures
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Study
HBP	Human Brain Project
HDRUK	Health Data Research UK
HPC	high-performance computing
HTA	Health Technology Assessments
HUGO	Human Genome Organisation
IBBL	Integrated BioBank of Luxembourg
ICF	Informed Consent Form
IDEA-FAST	Identifying Digital Endpoints to Assess Fatigue, Sleep and Activities of Daily Living in Neurodegenerative Disorders and Immune-mediated Inflammatory Diseases
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IMD	Implementation metadata discovery

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IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
IMI BIOMAP	(IMI) Biomarkers in Atopic Dermatitis and Psoriasis
IP	Intellectual Property
iPSC	induced Pluripotent Stem Cells
IRD	Implementation Record-level Discovery
IRDiRC	International Rare Diseases Research Consortium
ISO	International Standards Organisation
JPND	Joint Programming Initiative Neurodegenerative Diseases
KCL	Kings College London
KOL	Key Opinion Leaders
LIH-IBBL	Luxembourg Institute of Health/IBBL
LME	Linear Mixed Effects
LYG	Lygature
M	Milestone
MB	Management Board
MBL	Mannose-Binding Lectin
MCI	Mild Cognitive Impairment
MDTA	Material and Data Transfer Agreement
MINERVA	Molecular Interaction NEtwork VisuAlization
MIP	Medical Informatics Platform
MIRIADE-ITN	Multi-omics Interdisciplinary Research Integration to Address DEmentia diagnosis - Innovative Training Networks
MJFF	Michael J. Fox Foundation
MMSE	Mini-Mental State Examination
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MSA	Multiple System Atrophy
MTA	Material Transfer Agreement
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
NCDC	Netherlands Consortium Dementia Cohorts
NCER-PD	National Centre of Excellence in Research on Parkinson's Disease
NCRAD	(US) National Centralized Repository for Alzheimer's Disease and Related Dementias
NEURONET	IMI project to Create an overall platform for efficient collaboration, communication and operational synergies among present and future IMI neurodegenerative diseases projects
NDCN	Nuffield Department of Clinical Neurosciences
NFL	NeuroFilament Light chain
NICE	The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NOV	NOVARTIS PHARMA
NTK	NeuroToolKit
NWO	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (Dutch Research Council)
Olink	One protein biomarker platform
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
OPDC	Oxford Parkinson's Disease Centre
PACC	Preclinical Alzheimer Cognitive Composite

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PD	Parkinson's Disease
PEG	Patient Expert Group
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PHT	Personal Health Train
PI	Public Involvement
PI	Principal Investigator
PM	Programme Manager
PMID	PubMed Identification Number
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PPI	Public and Patient Involvement
PPMI	Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative
Prepad	Participant Registry in EPAD
Preclinical	Stage of Alzheimer's disease before the occurrence of the first clinical symptoms
Prodromal	Stage of Alzheimer's disease where there are obvious symptoms of brain dysfunction (mild cognitive impairment, MCI)
PSP	Progressive Supranuclear Palsy
Ptau	Phosphorylated tau protein
PUK	Parkinson UK
QC	Quality Control
RADAR	Remote Assessment of Disease and Relapse
RADAR-AD	Remote Assessment of Disease and Relapse – Alzheimer's Disease
RADAR-BASE	(Remote Assessment of Disease And Relapses) an open source platform to leverage data from wearables and mobile technologies
RADAR-CNS	Remote Assessment of Disease and Relapse – Central Nervous System
RBD	Isolated REM sleep Behaviour Disorder
RCEG	Research Community Expert Group
REM	Rapid Eye Movement
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
REMS	Risk Evaluation and Mitigation Strategy
SAF	Stakeholder Advisory Framework
SARD	SANOFI AVENTIS RECHERCHE & DEVELOPMENT
SAWP	Scientific Advice Working Party
SCD	Subjective Cognitive Decline
SDTM	Study Data Tabulation Model
SEND	SEND is an implementation of the SDTM standard for nonclinical studies.
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOLVE-RD	Solving the unsolved Rare Diseases
SOP	Standard Operation Procedure
SVAR	Svar Life Science AB
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
TCC	Terminal Complement Complex
TEVA	Teva Pharmaceutical Industries

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TMT proteomics	Tandem Mass Tag proteomics
TNF1	Tumor Necrosis Factor 1
TPP	Target Product Profile
TraIT	TRAnslational research IT
tranSMART	tranSMART is an open-source data warehouse designed to store large amounts of clinical data from clinical trials, as well as data from basic research, so that it can be interrogated together for translational research.
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UCB	UCB Biopharma
UGOT	University of Gothenburg
ULEIC	University of Leicester
UM	University Maastricht
UMC	University Medical Center
UMCG	University Medical Center Groningen
UNIGE	University of Geneva
UNILU	University of Luxembourg
UOXF	University of Oxford
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
VAD	Virtual Appliance Design
VD	Vascular Dementia
VUmc	Vrije Universiteit medisch centrum (Free University Medical center of Amsterdam)
WP	Work Package
ZonMw	ZorgOnderzoek Nederland Medische Wetenschappen (research counsel netherlands)

DEFINITIONS	
Term	Definition
Access rights	The rights to use Results or Background under the terms and conditions laid down in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement
Action/Project	All the activities, including research activities, carried out by the Beneficiaries as detailed in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement
Action Objective	The objectives of the Action as defined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement
Algorithm	A procedure used for solving a problem or performing a computation
Anonymous (Data)	Data which do not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person. Anonymous Data are not Personal Data as defined in GDPR
Anonymisation/Anonymised	The concerned Data do no longer relate to an identified or identifiable natural person. This means that Personal Data are rendered Anonymous in such a manner that the Data Subject is not or no longer identifiable (e.g. because all direct and indirect personal identifiers are removed from the Data by for instance implementing technical measures so that such data can no longer be linked back to the initial Data Subject and the Data Subject can therefore not be re-identified)
Application Programming Interface (API)	The application programming interface materials and related documentation containing all Data and information to allow skilled Software or Database developers to create Software or Database interfaces that interface or interact with other specified Software or Databases
Background	Any Data, Databases, Know-How or information, whatever its form or nature, tangible or intangible, including any rights such as Intellectual Property rights, that are: (i) held by the Beneficiaries prior to their accession to the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement, and (ii) identified by the Beneficiaries in accordance with Clause 5.1.1 or 5.1.2 of the Consortium Agreement as needed for implementing the Action or for Exploiting its Results. Background consists of (a) Algorithm Background; (b) Software Background; (c) Background Databases and (d) Other Background
(a) Algorithm Background	Any Background, both Software and non-Software which describes a procedure for solving a problem or performing a computation
(b) Software Background	Any Background which is Software
(c) Background Database	Any Background which is a Database
(d) Other Background	Background other than (a), (b), or (c)
Beneficiary/Beneficiaries	A legal entity who has signed the Grant Agreement with the IHI JU, either its main body or via a form of accession, and/or this Consortium Agreement, either by signing the main body of this Consortium Agreement or via a Form of Accession
Biometric Data	(as defined in the GDPR) Personal Data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data
Confidential Information	Any Data, documents or other material (in any form) that is marked as "confidential" or "secret" at the time it is disclosed or which has to be considered as confidential by a reasonable person. If information has been identified as confidential only orally, it will be considered to be Confidential Information only if such confidentiality is confirmed in writing within thirty (30) Days of the oral disclosure or if it has to be considered as confidential by a reasonable person. Notwithstanding the foregoing, Personal Data will always be considered as Confidential Information
Consent	(as defined in the GDPR) The Data Subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the Data Subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the Processing of Personal Data relating to him or her
Consortium Agreement	The consortium agreement for IHI Action IDERHA and all of its appendices, together with any amendments validly agreed in writing amongst the Beneficiaries
(Data) Controller	(as defined in the GDPR) The natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of Personal Data
Data	data, images, works or other independent elements
Database	(i) collection of data, images, works or other independent elements, arranged in a systematic or methodical manner, and individually accessible by electronic means or by any other means, whatever the medium, that have been the subject of a constitution, a matching, and / or an annotation, and / or an interpretation, and/or curation and / or other form of added value or by technical means allowing and / or facilitating said annotation; and (ii) Database management

	systems managing and controlling access to such Data, images, works or other independent elements (also referred to herein as “Database Platform Framework”), and includes (iii) the associated Database Documentation
Database Documentation	Documentation in written text and illustrations in relation to a Database and provides a description of what a particular Database does or shall do, how it operates and how it is supposed to be used. It includes the respective Database manuals and documentation for using the API
Data Protection Legislation	shall have the meaning set forth in Appendix 2 of the Consortium Agreement
Data Subject	An identified or identifiable natural person. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person
Days	Calendar days, as the case may be, unless otherwise specified
Donor	The natural person to whom the Human Samples refer
Exploitation/Exploiting	The use of Results in further teaching, research and innovation activities other than those covered by the Action, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. For the avoidance of doubt, “Exploitation” can be divided into (i) Research Use and (ii) Direct Exploitation. To illustrate the distinction between Research Use and Direct Exploitation, an example of Research Use is the application of Results (like an animal model or a biomarker) as a tool for research and clinical research in the discovery, development or commercialisation of pharmaceutical products by for-profit institutions and organisations. However, the commercialization of such biomarker itself as a diagnostic kit would be Direct Exploitation
(i) Research Use	The use of Results for all purposes other than for implementing the Action or for Direct Exploitation. For the avoidance of a doubt, such use includes but is not limited to the use of Results as a tool in teaching, research, development & innovation activities, including but not limited to use as a tool to support clinical research and trials on a product, and in standardization activities linked to such product. For the avoidance of doubt, the field of Research Use includes use of Results without limitation as specified in (a) and (b)
(a) for pharmaceuticals and vaccines	All pre-clinical research and development activities, all human clinical studies on compounds which were not Results of this Action (to the extent Results are used in such activities, e.g. as a tool), all activities relating to developing the ability to commercialize any drug substance or drug product (including process development work), all activities relating to seeking, obtaining and/or maintaining any regulatory approvals from regulatory authorities or for the purposes of a medicinal product assessment (as provided for in the applicable local legislation).
(b) for medical devices, medical, digital health and health data technologies and imaging techniques	All pre-clinical research and development activities, all clinical studies or data obtained in order to determine the utility of a particular medical device which was not a Result of the Action, the use of Results as a tool in all research & development steps taken (including use in tests) for development of a Beneficiary’s own medical device, medical, digital health and health data technologies and imaging techniques with a view to ultimately making available to the market such medical device, medical, digital health or health data technologies and imaging techniques, all activities relating to developing the ability to commercialize any drug substance or drug product (including process development work) in combination with a medical device, all tools used in the evaluation of design options for their suitability for commercialization, all activities relating to seeking, obtaining and/or maintaining any regulatory approvals from regulatory authorities for new and existing commercial products or for the purposes of registration of a medical device (as provided for in the applicable local legislation).
(ii) Direct Exploitation	Use for all direct commercialization purposes. For the avoidance of doubt, such use includes directly (i) providing commercial services with (or using) Results, sales of Results (or products incorporating such Results, for instance commercialisation of a diagnostic kit containing a biomarker to the extent the biomarker was a Result), or marketing for commercial services on, or sales of, Results, (ii) developing a Result (for instance clinical trial on an asset which is a Result) with a view to directly commercialize such Result (or products incorporating such Result), and (iii) manufacturing a Result (or products incorporating such Result), with a view to directly commercialize such Result (or products incorporating such Result). Examples of Direct Exploitation include (a) and (b)
(a) Phase 1	The use of the IDERHA Platform and all Action Objective Results consisting thereof, as a tool for further analysis, design, development, production, validation and/or distribution of pharmaceutical products or medical devices, digital health and health data technologies by for-profit organizations, which does not constitute any Phase 2 activities.

(b) Phase 2	Commercialization of the IDERHA Platform and all Action Objective Results consisting thereof, either by a non-profit or for-profit organization
Grant Agreement	Grant Agreement No. 101112135 (including its annexes and any amendments thereto) entered into between the Beneficiaries and the IHI JU for the undertaking by the Beneficiaries of the Action
Human Sample	Any human tissue or human biological material of a Donor, including any portion of an organ, any tissue, skin, bone, muscle, connective tissue, blood, cerebrospinal fluid, cells, gametes, or sub-cellular structures such as DNA, and/or any copy of such Donor's human tissue or human biological material (such as stem cells, cell lines or xenograft tissues which are genetically identical to the initially collected human materials of a Donor); and any human biological product, including, but not limited to, hair, nail clippings, teeth, urine, faeces, breast milk, and sweat but excluding derivatives and/or non-human progeny (for example a viral or bacterial strain obtained from any human biological material of the Donor)
IDERHA platform	The platform that will be developed in the Action which will consist of a set of individual tools and related processes (and relevant templates), most of which pre-existed separately, and will become integrated, made operable and can mutually use each other's services and devices into one infrastructure or eco-system. Collectively, these components will thus form an "open platform" which includes access to multi-modal data and can be scaled by simply connecting additional systems, data resources and additional services and tools, which can all leverage and participate in this platform. The IDERHA Platform is considered an "Action Objective Result" under the Consortium Agreement, however, it may consist of different Results, OSS Results and possibly of Third Party Proprietary Software (for the latter, under the conditions of the license on said Software, which will be compatible with the Access Rights granted under this Consortium Agreement).
IHI JU	The IHI Joint Undertaking, a European Union body established by Council Regulation (EU) No. 2021/2085 of 19 November 2021
In Kind Contributions to Additional Activities (IKAA)	Contributions by the private members of the IHI JU, their constituent entities or the affiliated entities of either, consisting of the costs incurred by them in implementing additional activities less any contribution to those costs from the IHI JU and from the participating states of the IHI JU where 'additional activities' are activities that do not receive financial support from the IHI JU or any other Union funding programme but (i) contribute to its objectives; (ii) are set out in the annual additional activities plan (the IKAA Plan) annexed to the IHI JU work programme, or alternatively, in a plan for additional activities included in relevant project proposals; (iii) are carried out in the Union or in countries associated with Horizon Europe (irrespective of the country of establishment of the entity incurring the related costs). Additional activities can be either Programme specific or Project specific: Programme-specific additional activities contribute to the uptake of results from IHI JU, IMI2 JU, IMI JU projects or have a significant added value for the Union; Project-specific additional activities contribute towards the achievement of objectives of the IHI JU funded projects, or the dissemination, sustainability or exploitation of IHI JU project results
IKAA Output	Any tangible or intangible output of performing the additional activities referred to in the definition of IKAA, such as data, Know-How or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including Intellectual Property rights
Intellectual Property	Knowledge in the broadest sense, encompassing e.g. inventions, Software, Databases and micro-organisms, whether or not they are protected by legal instruments such as patents, as referred to in Commission Recommendation C(2008) 1329 of 10.4.2018 on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities and the Code of Practice for universities and other public research institutions attached to that recommendation. For the avoidance of doubt and without limitation, Know-How, patent rights, copyrights, database rights, and trade secrets constitute Intellectual Property
Know-How	Any unpatented technical information (including, without limitation, information relating to inventions, discoveries, concepts, methodologies, models, research, development and testing procedures, the results of experiments, tests and trials, manufacturing processes, techniques and specifications, quality control data, analyses, reports and submissions) that is not in the public domain
Materials	All types of tangible chemical, biological and/or physical materials and any type of equipment and hardware
Metadata	Data which provides context about the Data. This is not limited to a description of the Data, but can include information about the structure of the Data, administrative information about e.g. provenance and legal aspects, and information providing insight into the quality of the Data
Open Access	Online access, provided free of charge to the end-user, to Research Outputs resulting from the Action, in accordance with Articles 14 and 39(3) of the Horizon Europe Regulation

Open Source Software (OSS)	Software that is owned by a Beneficiary or Third Party and that is made available under the terms of an OSS license, which adopts a licensing or distribution model that allows the licensee to disclose, distribute or otherwise make available to the licensor and/or other persons the source code to any modifications or derivative work used or created by or on behalf of the licensee. OSS can be freely accessed, used, changed and shared (in modified or unmodified form) by anyone. The internationally recognized definition for OSS and a list with all OSI-approved OSS licenses can be found on the website of the Open Source Initiative (OSI) (https://opensource.org/osd-annotated)
Personal Data	Any information relating to a Data Subject, including data extracted from Human Samples, if and to the extent they refer or can be referred to an identified or identifiable Donor. Data (including data extracted from Human Samples) that are Anonymized are no longer considered to be Personal Data. Data that are Anonymous are not Personal Data. Personal Data has the same meaning as defined in the GDPR
Personal Data Breach	(as defined in the GDPR) A breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, Personal Data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed
Process(ing)	(as defined in the GDPR) Any operation or set of operations which is performed on Personal Data or sets of Personal Data whether or not by automated means, such as the obtaining, collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure, by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction
(Data) Processor	(as defined in the GDPR) A natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes Personal Data on behalf of the Controller
Profiling	(as defined in the GDPR) Any form of automated processing of Personal Data consisting of the use of Personal Data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements
Providing Beneficiary	shall have the meaning set forth in Clause 8.1.1 of the Consortium Agreement relating to the transfer of Materials
Pseudonymisation/Pseudonymised	(as defined in the GDPR) The processing of Personal Data in such a manner that the Personal Data can no longer be attributed to a specific Data Subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the Personal Data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person
Results	Any tangible or intangible Effect of the Action, such as Data, new Databases, new Software, Know-How or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including Intellectual Property rights. For the avoidance of doubt, "Results" can be subdivided into (i) Action Objective Results and (ii) Sideground Results, but excludes any IKA Output
(i) Action Objective Results	Any Results generated during the term of the Action and in the performance of the activities set out in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and which are inside the scope of the Action Objectives. Action Objective Results consists of (a) Operational Improvement Results; (b) Software Results; (c) OSS Results, (d) Algorithm Results, and (e) Database Results, (f) Imaging Results and (g) Other Results
(a) Operational Improvement Results	Any Action Objective Results which are non-software Results that are not in code form (such as newly discovered uses to existing code) and expand, improve, or enhance the use and potential value related to any Beneficiary's Algorithm Background or Software Background
(b) Software Results	Any Action Objective Results which is a Software
(c) OSS Results	Any and all Software Results that are made available as soon as developed as OSS during the Action under the terms and conditions of the Preferred OSS License or another OSS license (published on the website of the Open Source Initiative)
(d) Algorithm Results	Action Objective Results which are output from an Algorithm, such as (but not limited to) subject level output from an Algorithm representing a clinical insight. For the avoidance of doubt, excluding Operational Improvement Results
(e) Database Results	Any Action Objective Result which is a Database
(f) Imaging Results	Any Action Objective Results which are related to imaging data
(g) Other Results	Action Objective Results other than (a), (b), (c), (d), (e), (f)
(ii) Sideground Results	Any Results generated during the term of the Action and under the performance of the activities set out in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, but which are outside the Action Objectives

Research Outputs	Results generated by the Action to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, data or other engineered outcomes and processes such as Software, algorithms, protocols and electronic notebooks
Research Use	Shall have the meaning set forth in the definition of Exploitation
Royalty-Free	For the envisaged grant of Access Rights, free of charge or any other payment
Software	A software program – other than a Database - being sequences of instructions to carry out a process in, or convertible into, a form executable by a computer, and fixed in any tangible medium of expression. A Software shall constitute its corresponding (i) Software Documentation, (ii) Object Code and (iii) Source Code
(i) Object Code	Software in machine-readable compiled and/or executable form including, but not limited to, binary code form and in form of machine-readable libraries used for linking procedures and functions to other Software
(ii) Source Code	Software in human-readable form normally used to make modifications to it, including but not limited to comments and procedural code such as job control language and scripts to control compilation and installation
(iii) Software Documentation	Documentation in written text and illustrations in relation to a Software and provides a description of what a particular software does or shall do, how it operates and how it is supposed to be used. It includes the respective software manuals and documentation for using the API
Synthetic Data	Artificial data that is generated from original data and a model that is trained to reproduce the characteristics and structure of the original data. This means that synthetic data and original data should deliver very similar results when undergoing the same statistical analysis
Third Party	A legal entity or person which is not a party to the Grant Agreement nor the Consortium Agreement, including a legal entity or person only providing resources to a Beneficiary
Third Party Proprietary Software	Software that is owned or controlled by a Third Party and that is made available under specific license terms (other than OSS license terms). A Beneficiary who intends to contribute Third Party Proprietary Software in the Project, must first make sure that the Access Rights that will apply to such Third Party Proprietary Software under this Consortium Agreement, are compatible with the applicable Software license. For the avoidance of doubt, Third Party Proprietary Software excludes OSS
User	Any natural person given Access to the entire IDERHA Platform or parts thereof